

INFLUENCE OF STAKEHOLDER INVOLVEMENT ON THE PERFORMANCE OF SWM PROJECTS IN KATOR BLOCK, JUBA, SOUTH SUDAN

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Abstract: Performance of solid waste management projects in Juba City remains a challenge and becomes an issue in developmental projects mainly in environment due to lack of policy framework, governance, insecurity including inefficient utilization resources, schedule delays in completing activities and achieving milestone in South Sudan. Juba, the capital, environmental pollution is now a serious issue in the city, which makes the citizens' lives less sanitary and sometimes unsafe. As a result, the Juba City Council must create a strategy to enhance the effectiveness of the solid waste management initiatives inside each Block. Therefore, this study sought to investigate the influence of stakeholder involvement on performance of SWM projects in Kator Block, Juba, South Sudan. A descriptive survey research design was used in the study. The study focused on three active solid waste management initiatives and used 200 respondents as a sample. Primary data for the study were gathered via a semi-structured questionnaire. For this study, data in both quantitative and qualitative forms were gathered. Quantitative data was analyzed and presented in tables, charts, and graphs using descriptive statistics like mean and standard deviation. Using multiple regression analysis and correlation analysis, two forms of inferential statistics, the study examined the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. These were made with the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.0. The results of the study showed that the performance of SWM projects in Kator Block, Juba, South Sudan, was positively significantly impacted by stakeholder involvement. The study comes to the conclusion that stakeholders are an integral part of every business and project, and that their participation and contribution ensures any project's success. The study recommends that it is crucial for all stakeholders to fully understand the goals and processes of a project in order to guarantee its success.

Keywords: Stakeholder Involvement, Project Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

The success of a project is determined by various factors such as its complexity, contractual agreements, the relationships between the parties involved, the skills of the project manager, and the capabilities of the other parties (Anantatmula, 2019). According to Cao and Hoffman (2021), a project's performance is typically evaluated and quantified in terms of the metrics that depend on it. These metrics refer to the standard procedures used to gather and display relevant data regarding project effectiveness, efficiency, and inputs. Therefore, project performance can be assessed by looking at how much was spent, how long it took, how successfully the project met the users' needs and how well it performed in terms of quality.

The project manager organizes and oversees project resources in order to accomplish the objectives outlined in the project plan. They ensure that the project stays on schedule by implementing thorough monitoring and control procedures, ultimately ensuring that the final deliverable meets the customer's acceptance criteria. This is known as the implementation phase (Crawford & Bryce, 2017). According to Slevin and Pinto (2020), any agreed-upon improvements are put into

practice during the project implementation phase, which also makes sure that the final deliverables match the client's acceptance criteria through rigorous monitoring and control procedures. Therefore, to ensure that the project remains within its projected scope and budget, the implementation process involves effectively managing resources and monitoring performance.

People's consumption is impacted by globalization, as they use more solid materials and produce more solid waste over time. Leton and Omotosho (Yong, 2018) define solid waste as the byproducts of undesired human activity that are neither liquid nor gaseous, such as trash, junk, and refuse. The production of municipal solid waste (MSW) rises in tandem with the rate of development of any given nation. The world's first Global Waste Management Outlook (GWMO), published in 2015 by the United Nations Environment Programme and the International Solid Waste Association, estimates that over two billion people lack access to waste collection services and that over three billion people dispose of their waste carelessly, often burning it outside. There have been references to this as a global waste emergency or crisis (Wilson & Webster, 2018).

Globally speaking, developing Asia and the continent of South America are the two regions where waste management initiatives have had comparable effects. For instance, the 2019 government report from India demonstrates that the country's urban population has been growing. It causes emissions from manufacturing, overexploitation, and climate change, among other environmental problems. In particular, it produces trillions of tons of solid and non-solid waste annually (UNEP, 2021). Nonetheless, it is crucial to emphasize that various waste management programs and initiatives in India have benefited the populace in a number of ways of the Republic of India, as demonstrated by Nandan, Yadav, Baksi, et al. (2019). Positive effects that are included are; methane recovery in the treatment of wastewater, the production of renewable energy, and the reduction of air pollution brought on by the careless disposal and burning of municipal solid waste (MSW). One of the financial advantages of these projects in India is the creation of jobs at the captive power plant. Water pollution is reduced, infectious disease cases are decreased, organic manure made from waste from the biogas production chamber is sold to surrounding farmers, etc.

With 38% urbanization, Africa is recognized as the least developed continent in the world. While this may seem insignificant in comparison to numerous other nations, African nations are undergoing swift development, with an annual growth rate of four percent (Bello, Ismail & Kabbashi, 2016). African nations are currently dealing with an enormous volume of MSW, which directly affects the environment, public health, and safety. According to Kassahum and Birara (2018), five waste-management firms, also referred to as micro and small enterprises, and one private limited company, Dream Light PLC, are used by the municipality of Bahir Dar in Ethiopia to collect solid waste. According to OECD studies (2020), the nation's numerous waste management initiatives that have been launched over the last five years have been linked to a number of positive effects. Jobs for people hired by municipalities to handle waste are among the subjects discussed, along with national revenue collection, increased productivity from recycling waste materials like plastics, and a decline in health issues in areas where proper disposal has taken place.

Njogu (2018) found that while many organizations—including the federal government, local governments, NGOs, CBOs, and different businesses through PPPs programs—have proposed a number of projects to help lessen the detrimental effects of waste in urban centers, particularly in the slums, not much has actually been accomplished. She conducted interviews with 100 respondents and discovered that 76% of them stated that the basic objective of different waste management programs is to collect both liquid and solid waste in one area and let it decompose. This has exposed over 72% of the nearby residents to social conflicts, health risks, and other issues. Another study conducted in Nairobi County by Ajega and Genga (2019) reveals that various government agencies, local communities, non-governmental organizations, etc., have started projects aimed at resolving the long-standing problems related to urban waste in residential estates and industrial centers. Ajega and Genga point out that although Kenya has come a long way in terms of waste management, many of its initiatives still need to address problems like recycling and have placed a lot of focus on the dumping of both solid and sewage waste.

The most crucial aspect of project performance, according to Choudhry and Iqbal (2018), is preventing the project from going over budget, from taking longer than expected to receive approvals, from failing to adhere to the technical requirements for functionality, safety, quality, and environmental preservation, and from not finishing on time for design and occupancy. According to Kululanga and Kuotcha (2019), project performance guarantees that businesses maximize profits, reduce the effects of uncertain and risky events to accomplish project goals, and take advantage of opportunities for risky events to arise.

Stakeholder involvement, according to Achterkamp and Vos (2018), is a process that involves incorporating the public's needs, concerns, and values into decision-making during project management. It is predicated on a two-way exchange of

information and interaction between the organization making the decision and the people who will be involved in the project. Effective stakeholder engagement techniques, according to Magassouba, Tambi, Alkhlaifat, and Abdullah (2019), enable the gathering of vital data about the stakeholders who are impacted by a project. Thus, having access to this data presents a chance to develop project plans that will benefit all parties involved.

Projects for solid waste management are part of the capacity development portfolio, supported by both JICA and non-JICA funding sources, and they work in tandem with the other donors. The Juba Clean City Project, the Project for Capacity Development in Solid Waste Management in Juba, and the Data Collection Survey on Solid Waste Management in Juba, Republic of South Sudan, are the main elements of the solid waste management initiatives. With the ultimate goal of enabling Juba City Council to conduct solid waste management according to a plan, the projects were carried out to realize the project purpose of establishing the fundamental framework of solid waste management in Juba City, gathering fundamental data for waste management planning, and identifying the needs and priorities.

For centuries, solid waste management has been a problem in many nations, affecting both urban and rural areas (Ibrahim, Al-Kindi, Qureshi, Magharwry, 2022). Solid waste is a valuable resource that has numerous negative effects on the environment and human health, but it can also be used to generate energy and make money. The composition, attributes, and qualities of solid waste are determined by its source (Ibrahim, Al-Kindi, Qureshi, Magharwry, 2022). Immediate, sustainable action is needed to lessen community vulnerability, but South Sudan lacks the domestic resources to address waste management issues. Therefore, in order to facilitate and expedite national environmental management, support in the form of funding, technology, and capacity-building will be required.

At the time of planning, there was no structure to manage solid waste in Juba City and solid waste in the city was an environmental and health problem. The importance of solid waste management was recognized in legal document, as stipulated in the Local Government Act and Environmental Protection Bill that the local governments were responsible for the solid waste management. Thus, the project was consistent with the development policies and needs of South Sudan. The project was also consistent with the Japan's ODA policy, which indicated support to the improvement of basic living as one of its major areas of assisting South Sudan.

Moreover, that the project aimed to improve people's lives just after the internal conflicts, and that project carefully proceeded with pilot activity target areas selection so as not to let people feel unfairness between different tribes and communities was an appropriate approach for a project implemented in a conflict-affected country. Good SWM service is the first step towards realizing a healthy population for the whole country (JCC, 2022). However, the project is facing performance challenges because of the lack of management resources such as human resources, goods, money, and information for SWM. Juba Waste Management Plan (2015-2023) as a Master Plan is the first long-term plan for Solid Waste Management (SWM) in Juba City, South Sudan the purpose of which is to achieve a Clean and Green Juba City. The project has suffered performance issues exacerbated by the repeated armed conflict that necessitated the project to be postponed for the past 8 years. It has recently been reinstated.

UNEP is assisting Juba City Council and other local organizations in South Sudan in enhancing their waste management practices. Various efforts have been undertaken to enhance waste management in Juba through collaborations with the Ministry of Environment, Juba City Council, Juba County Council, Payams (administrative areas), development partners, and non-governmental organizations. These endeavors encompass conducting an initial environmental assessment of the existing Juba dump site to assess the impact of indiscriminate disposal of municipal solid waste on the environment. Additionally, there is a concerted effort to improve the welfare of waste pickers at the disposal site by providing them with protective gear and establishing health and safety guidelines; an examination of the current organizational framework, legal framework, operational protocols, and accessible resources concerning the provision of solid waste management services; educating the public about recycling and waste management by establishing environmental clubs, hosting workshops on the subject, and providing waste management training to journalists; An examination of the makeup of waste to produce trustworthy information that will serve as the foundation for creating and implementing waste and recycling systems in Juba.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Every project has a distinct set of performance requirements because projects vary in value, size, and complexity. According to Baptista, Santos, Pascoa and Sandig (2020) a project's failure can be brought on by a number of organizational system-

related issues, such as unclear project objectives, a shoddy project schedule, numerous changes, inadequate control, poor communication, unclear stakeholder roles, and a lack of top management support. Garang (2021) observe that in South Sudan, between one and two thirds of the produced solid waste are not gathered. This leads to the careless disposal of the uncollected waste in drainage channels and streets, where it is frequently combined with animal and human excrement. Furthermore, it appears that the procedures currently in place for gathering, processing, and discarding municipal solid wastes are inadequate. Some common project performance issues and their potential like schedule delay may cause delays in completing activities and achieving milestones. These include poor planning, unrealistic timelines, inadequate resource allocation, dependencies on external factors, scope changes, or unexpected obstacles. Cost overruns projects sometimes exceed the allocated budget and consequently result into inaccurate cost estimation, scope changes, poor budget management, unforeseen expenses, inefficient resource utilization, or procurement issues. Addressing project performance issues required proactive measures such as revisiting project plans, adjusting timelines and resources, improving communication and stakeholder engagement, enhancing risk management practices and providing necessary support and training to the project team.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Literature Review

Stakeholder Theory

According to Edward Freeman's 1983 stakeholder theory, there are parties within an organization that have an impact on how it operates. This theory's proponents, like Atkin and Skitmore (2008), The inclusion of stakeholders and consideration of their needs is imperative for any organization. According to the theory, companies have a higher chance of success in their ventures if they can consider the interests of most stakeholders. Understanding the different kinds of stakeholders in an organization and their impact on it is necessary to apply this theory.

Manowong and Ogunlana (2010) and other critics of the theory contend that it lacks sufficient specificity and is therefore difficult to operationalize in a way that would permit scientific verification. In addition, the theory falls short in providing sufficient guidance for making decisions, such as reducing the conflicts of interest that frequently occur when trying to satisfy the varied demands of different organizational stakeholders. However, the theory has been used to highlight how important it is to take stakeholders' interests into account when making business decisions.

The theory applies to this study because it emphasizes the importance of considering a wide range of stakeholders when undertaking infrastructure projects in order to ensure success for road contractors and other parties involved. Therefore, An organization must be able to adapt its way of working in order to satisfy its stakeholders, manage their expectations, and ensure that the main objective of finishing the tasks assigned is fulfilled. The involvement of stakeholders and the projects' social impact play a major role in determining how well road infrastructure projects perform. Additionally, the study recognizes how crucial it is to engage in negotiations with stakeholders in order to guarantee the successful completion of road infrastructure projects. Therefore the stakeholder theory is critical in answering the first objective of this study which is stakeholder involvement and how it influences performance.

Empirical Literature Review

In a study involving projects carried out with stakeholder participation, Callahan (2017) found that proponents of participatory processes assert that these methods enhance social capital, advance democracy, lessen conflict, foster accountability, and advance fairness and justice. Conversely, detractors wrote off involvement as unproductive, expensive, laborious, ill-informed politically, irrational, disruptive, and with limited representation. The study also found that participation provides a mechanism for obtaining the consent of the governed in more precise ways than is practical for the implementation of projects such as solid waste management, and that it also has the added benefit of reducing litigation and adversarial encounters. Nonetheless, there is a methodological flaw because the respondents were chosen on purpose.

According to a study by Zaman (2017), including communities in waste management initiatives frequently results in publicity featuring waste management advice, which ultimately reduces waste. In a similar vein, Mpinda et al. (2016)'s study shows that public awareness and responsibility issues are the two main subsets of waste management drivers. In order to guarantee sustainable waste management, public participation is essential. It begins with employees being aware of the types of waste that a company produces and the best techniques for handling, minimizing, and discarding waste.

According to a study by Kassahum and Birara (2018) on the Assessment of Solid Waste Management Practices in Bahir Dar City, Ethiopia, the municipality has chosen to provide solid waste management services to the locals once a week. However, the survey's findings show that only 29% of sample households had weekly access to solid waste management services, suggesting that the program's effectiveness could be improved. Of the 350 households, 66.6% dispose of solid waste illegally, and 33.4% wait for waste collectors to visit their neighborhood to remove the waste. Hence, the enhancement of the existing inadequate condition of solid waste management services relies significantly on the engagement of urban households, micro and small enterprises, as well as governmental and non-governmental organizations. However, the study context was Bahir Dar City, Ethiopia thus presenting a contextual gap.

Ngundo and James (2018) investigated government project implementation in Machakos County, Kenya, as well as project management techniques. Targeted were 128 projects carried out by the Machakos County Government. According to the study's findings, project managers did not take users' needs into account for every outcome. It was not encouraged for users to have a say in any corrective actions taken during project implementation or to share project ownership. The project implementation was largely unsuccessful due to the absence of opportunities for users and stakeholders to benefit from the project's execution and assume responsibility during the system's commencement. Consequently, the stakeholders were unable to be held responsible for the results of specific activities and processes that were carried out.

In a 2019 study, Onchong'a, Mutiso, and Monyenye examined how stakeholder participation affected the way solid waste management projects were carried out in Kenya's Nyamira County. It was discovered that there was a strong positive correlation between the execution of solid waste management projects in Kenya's Nyamira County and stakeholder involvement. It was discovered that stakeholder involvement was extremely important. In light of these findings, it was recommended that the County involve stakeholders in the solid waste management implementation process. Early on in SWM projects, the county government should identify and involve all relevant parties. This would guarantee that the project's stakeholders' interests and worries were identified, taken into account, and resolved. Involving pertinent parties would also help with monitoring and assessment as SWM projects are being implemented. However, the demographics of Nyamira, where the study was conducted, differ from those of the Juba City Council.

The study conducted by Ronnoh and Muchelule (2019) investigated how project management techniques affected Kericho County's solid waste operations. Additionally, the research study used a straightforward random sample method. The study's findings demonstrated a significant, favorable relationship between SW project performance and project planning. Furthermore, there was a clear and substantial link between the success of SW projects and the project stakeholders. The study discovered a moderate but significant correlation between project risk and the success of SW projects in Kericho County. However, the study sampled respondents using simple random sampling technique thus presenting a contextual gap.

Jolie (2021) investigated the effects on organizational sustainability of solid waste management strategies used by manufacturing companies in Beni, the Democratic Republic of the Congo. The results of the study showed that 49.02% of workers in Beni City's manufacturing companies generally agreed that improving organizational sustainability greatly depends on public participation in solid waste management. Additional research revealed that 66.957% of the workforce generally agreed that environmental and economic factors have a significant impact on improving the organizational sustainability of manufacturing companies. Additionally, the majority of workers, or 73.27%, concurred that managing solid waste and improving organizational sustainability are greatly impacted by resource efficiency. However, the study focused on solid waste management strategies adopted by manufacturing companies thus presenting a contextual gap.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A descriptive survey research design was used in the study. The study focused on three active solid waste management initiatives and used 200 respondents as a sample. Primary data for the study were gathered via a semi-structured questionnaire. For this study, data in both quantitative and qualitative forms were gathered. Quantitative data was analyzed and presented in tables, charts, and graphs using descriptive statistics like mean and standard deviation. Using multiple regression analysis and correlation analysis, two forms of inferential statistics, the study examined the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. These were made with the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.0.

4. FINDINGS

The descriptive statistics results on stakeholder involvement are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Stakeholder Involvement

Statement	SA	A	N	D	SD	M	Std.Dev
	%	%	%	%	%		
Participation in the project's decision-making process and cooperation on a common understanding.	41.2	34.1	12.9	8.2	3.5	3.96	0.445
fosters a culture of trust by providing a forum for stakeholders to voice their concerns and make their issues known.	35.3	49.4	4.7	4.7	5.9	4.43	1.219
guarantees that the project is held responsible for its deeds and promotes openness in its workings.	38.8	55.3	3.5	2.4	0.0	4.78	0.782
Verifies that the project plans appropriately reflect the needs and priorities that exist in the real world.	36.5	49.4	11.8	2.4	0.0	4.10	1.670
Makes it possible for stakeholders' voices to be heard, which raises trust	45.9	44.7	0.0	5.9	3.5	4.69	0.579
Aggregate Score	40.1	45.8	6.8	5.1	2.1	4.41	0.916

The respondents strongly agreed with the statements that stakeholder involvement ensures that the project is held accountable for its actions and promotes transparency in the project's actions, scoring a mean of 4.78 and a standard deviation of 0.782. Of those surveyed, 55.3% agreed, 3.5% said they were neutral, 2.4% disagreed, and 38.8% strongly agreed. The results corroborate those of Magassouba, Tambi, Alkhlaifat, and Abdullah (2019), who note that efficient stakeholder engagement techniques enable the gathering of vital data regarding the stakeholders impacted by a project.

The respondents strongly agreed with the statement that stakeholder involvement raises trust levels because it gives stakeholders' voices a voice (mean score of 4.69, standard deviation of 0.579). 45.9% strongly agreed, 44.7% agreed, 5.9% disagreed, and 3.5% strongly disagreed with the responses. The outcomes are consistent with the conclusions drawn by Achterkamp and Vos (2018), who proposed that stakeholder involvement is a process through which the public's needs, values, and concerns are taken into account when making decisions during project management and it is based on a two-way communication and interaction between the organization making the decision and the people that the people to be involved in the project.

The respondents' overwhelming agreement, as evidenced by a mean score of 4.51 and a standard deviation of 0.799, highlights the presence of a shared understanding and active participation in the decision-making process of the project. Specifically, 39.5% strongly agreed with this notion, while 46.6% agreed. A smaller percentage of 6.8% remained neutral, while 4.7% disagreed, and 2.6% strongly disagreed. These findings align with the research conducted by Edelenbos and Klijn (2020), affirming that involving stakeholders in decision-making can foster diverse perspectives and viewpoints, ultimately leading to a more comprehensive comprehension of the matter at hand.

The respondents' consensus on the importance of stakeholder involvement in fostering trust is evident from the mean score of 4.43 and standard deviation of 1.219. A significant portion of the respondents, 35.3%, strongly agreed with this statement, while 49.4% agreed. A small percentage, 4.7%, expressed neutrality or disagreement, and 5.9% strongly disagreed. The results are consistent with Taut's (2018) observation that stakeholder involvement improves the credibility of services and strengthens democracy by fostering understanding of the issues, lowering uncertainty, and fostering trust, all of which contribute to the successful implementation of projects.

The respondents agreed that stakeholder involvement guarantees that the project plans reflect the actual needs and priorities. The mean score of 4.10 and standard deviation of 1.670 provide evidence that the respondents' opinions were varied. Among them, 36.5% strongly agreed, 49.4% agreed, 11.8% were neutral, and 2.4% disagreed with the statement. These results align with the findings of Brandon and Fukunaga (2020), who emphasized the importance of the consultation process in understanding local contexts, addressing concerns, and contributing to project goals and outcomes.

In terms of the project's decision-making process, the respondents agreed on the existence of a shared understanding and involvement, as indicated by the mean score of 3.96 and standard deviation of 0.445. Specifically, 41.2% strongly agreed, 34.1% agreed, 12.9% were neutral, 8.2% disagreed, and 3.5% strongly disagreed with this statement. This finding supports the observation made by Pollock, Synnot, Nunn, Hill, and Morley (2021) that effective communication serves as the foundation for stakeholder consultation. It highlights the importance of creating and disseminating relevant information, fostering meaningful relationships, building trust, and actively listening to public input.

Results of Inferential Analysis

Table 2: Correlation Analysis

		Stakeholder involvement	Project performance
Stakeholder involvement	Pearson Correlation	1	.827**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	195	195

According to Table 4.13's results, stakeholder involvement's Pearson r value on project performance was 0.827, with a significance value of 0.000, meaning it was less than 0.05. This indicates that the participation of stakeholders was strongly correlated with the performance of SWM projects in Kator Block, Juba, South Sudan.

Regression Analysis Results

Table 3: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.876 ^a	.767	.756	1.025

According to Table 3 results, the adjusted R square value was 0.756, or 75.6%, indicating the degree to which the performance of SWM projects in Kator Block, Juba, South Sudan was explained by the stakeholder involvement. Thus, other variables not examined are accounted for by the remaining percentage (24.4%).

Table 4: Analysis of Variance

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	112.017	1	112.017	431.854	.001
	Residual	50.321	193	.259		
	Total	117.338	194			

The results are shown in Table 4 show that at 0.001, the significance value is less than 0.05. The F statistic (431.854) is greater than mean square value (112.017) is significant (p-value<0.05). Therefore, the model appropriate in determining how stakeholder involvement affects the performance of SWM projects in Kator Block, Juba, South Sudan.

Table 5: Regression Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
(Constant)	.704	.218		3.229	.000
Stakeholder involvement	.812	.336	4.130	2.417	.001

The results presented in Table 5 indicate that the performance of SWM projects in Kator Block, Juba, South Sudan would be at 0.704 when stakeholder involvement is held constant.

This was the regression equation that was determined;

$$\text{Project performance} = 0.704 + 0.812 (\text{stakeholder involvement})$$

Stakeholder involvement was measured in terms of sharing information, making decisions, and having expertise. The study concluded that more SWM projects in Kator Block, Juba, South Sudan would perform better if stakeholders were more involved. According to Table 5 results, stakeholder involvement had a positive β -value of 4.130 and a significance value of 0.001. This indicates that stakeholder participation significantly improved the performance of SWM projects in Juba, South

Sudan's Kator Block. The results are consistent with the research conducted by Ronnoh and Muchelule (2019), which looked at how project management techniques affected Kericho County's solid waste system's performance.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The study concludes that stakeholders are an essential part of every project and company. Any project is guaranteed to succeed due to the stakeholder involvement and contribution. A project's objectives are translated into goals through effective stakeholder engagement, which also guarantees that everyone involved in the project is on board. Every stakeholder has a different viewpoint on how to make the project and organization successful. Consensus and shared understanding are essential for fostering the project's positive momentum and vision.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

The study suggests that in order to guarantee a project's success, it is essential that all stakeholders have a comprehensive comprehension of the objectives and procedures. To facilitate this, it is recommended to arrange a series of interactive meetings in which stakeholders can interact and discuss the project. This will help to foster a sense of progress, optimism, engagement, and momentum. To achieve this, the project should be structured around the involvement of stakeholders. Determining the project's benefits and drawbacks is critical for each stakeholder and their respective areas of interest.

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